

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF AERIAL PARTS OF *DODONAEAVISCOSA* (L.) JACQ

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 25/06/2018

Available online

31/07/2018

Keywords

Dodonaeviscosa,
Pheretimaphostuma,
Anthelmintic Activity.

ABSTRACT

Helminthic infections are the most common infection in human beings affecting a large proportion of the world's population. Anthelmintic drugs are the drugs which are used to kill or reduce the number of helminthic parasites in the intestinal tract or tissues of the body. The aim of the present study highlights the evaluation of anthelmintic activity of *Dodonaeviscosa* aerial part extracts in experimental adult Indian earth worm *pheretimaphostuma*. Chloroform and ethanol extract of *Dodonaeviscosa* were investigated for anthelmintic activity using albendazole (10mg/ml) as standard reference and normal saline as control. The time to achieve paralysis and death of worm were determined. Chloroform extract shows more anthelmintic activity than ethanolic extract when compared with standard Albendazole.

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Please cite this article in press as **R. Xavier Arulappa** et al. Anthelmintic Activity of Aerial Parts of *Dodonaeviscosa* (L.) Jacq. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(07).

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INTRODUCTION

Helminthiasis or infection with parasitic worm is pathogenic for human beings. Immature forms of the parasites invade human beings via the skin or gastrointestinal tract (GIT) and evolve into well differentiated adult worms that have characteristics tissue distribution. Anthelmintics are drugs that may act locally to expel worms from the GIT or systematically to eradicate adult helminths or development forms that invade organs and tissues. Most of the existing anthelmintic produces side effects such as abdominal pain, loss of appetite, nausea, vomiting, headache and diarrhoea¹. Chemotherapy is the only treatment and effective tool to cure and control helminths infection, as effective vaccines against helminths have not been developed so far. Indiscriminate use of synthetic anthelmintic can lead to resistance of parasites². Most diseases caused by helminths are of a chronic and debilitating in nature³ and could be of value in preventing the development of resistance⁴. *Dodonaeaviscosa* (L.) Jacq. Presblongs to the family Sapindaceae⁵ and it is a dioecious or monoeciously stemmed shrub small tree upto 7 meter tall, known as mullukolinji commonly found in south india on dry barren lands on the coast to the Coimbatore, Madurai and Tirunelveli Districts. Subtropical and warm temperate region of Africa, southern asia and Australia⁶. The phytochemical studies revealed the leaves consist of alkaloid, flavonoids, carbohydrate Tannins, Phenols, Phytosterols, Saponins, Glycosides, Protein and amino acid, Fixed oils & fats⁷⁻⁸. The plant traditionally used as Anthelmintic, Anti pyretic, Anti inflammatory, Anti allergic, Anti diabetic, Anti bacterial, Anti fertility, Anti cancer, Analgesic, Anti oxidant, and hyper lipidemic effect. *Dodonaeaviscosa* possesses Anti oxidant, Anti diabetic, Anti bacterial activities⁹. This plant is related to *Dodonaea* species. So far the Anthelmintic activity was not confirmed in this plant and it's related species. Hence steps taken whether this plant possesses the above property and to check other phytochemical constituents.

EXPERIMENTAL

Plant Material

The aerial parts of *Dodonaeaviscosa* was collected from Tirunelveli district in September 2017 and authenticated by Dr.G.Johnsichristobel., Ph.D. Head of the Department & Research center, Department of Botany, Marthandam-629 165, Kanyakumari District. A voucher specimen of *Dodonaeaviscosa* (SARPC/RXA/CC-285) was deposited in the department of pharmaceutical chemistry in S.A.Raja Pharmacy College, Tirunelveli for future reference. The air dried aerial parts of the plant material was dried at room temperature, pulverized by a mechanical grinder, sieved through 40 mesh and then stored in an air tight and light resistant container for further use.

Preparation of extract

About 1 kg of coarsely powdered plant material was first extracted with chloroform for 72 hours. The extract was concentrated using rotary evaporator to get solid residue. The marc left was removed, dried and successively extracted with ethanol by hot percolation until complete extraction was effected. It was then concentrated under reduced pressure and finally dried in desiccators.

Anthelmintic Activity

The anthelmintic activity was evaluated on earth worms (8 ±1cm in length) washed with normal saline to remove all the extraneous matter as previously described¹⁰⁻¹². The assay was performed on adult Indian earth worm due to its anatomical and physiological resemblance with the intestinal round worm parasite of human beings¹³⁻¹⁵. The worms were divided into eight groups with six worms in each group and released into appropriately labeled petri dishes with the solvent composition shown in Table 1 that were made up to 50 ml with with normal saline and then evaluated for anthelmintic activity.

Table 1: Treatment groups of the worms and the solvents into which they were kept.

Group	Worm released into
1*	50 ml of 1% gum acacia in normal saline
2**	50 ml albendazole 10 mg/ml
3	50 ml chloroform extract 10 mg in 1% gum acacia in normal saline
4	50 ml chloroform extract 25 mg in 1% gum acacia in normal saline
5	50 ml chloroform extract 50 mg in 1% gum acacia in normal saline
6	50 ml ethanol extract, 10 mg in 1% gum acacia in normal saline
7	50 ml ethanol extract, 25 mg in 1% gum acacia in normal saline
8	50 ml ethanol extract, 50 mg in 1% gum acacia in normal saline

*control; **standard

Observations were made for the time taken for paralysis and death of individual worms to occur. For each worm, paralysis was said to have occurred when it was not able to move even in normal saline and death was concluded when it lost its motility followed with fading away of its body color¹⁶. Death was also confirmed by dipping the worm in slightly warm water and the mortality of the parasite was assumed to have occurred when all signs of movement had ceased¹⁷. The mean paralysis time and mean lethal time of the worms for the standard and each extract were recorded.

Table2: Anthelmintic activity of various extract of *Dodonaeviviscosa*.

Groups	Treatment	Time taken for paralysis (min)	Time taken for death (min)
I	Control	-	-
II	Albendazole (10mg/ml)	35.78 ± 0.22	62.83 ± 0.22
III	Chloroform extract (10mg/ml)	43.8 ± 0.18	77.67 ± 0.23
IV	Chloroform extract (25mg/ml)	25.69 ± 0.33***	50.64 ± 0.21***
V	Chloroform extract (50mg/ml)	17.76 ± 0.31***	36.04 ± 0.17***
VI	Ethanol extract (10mg/ml)	62.69 ± 0.26	112.0 ± 0.32
VII	Ethanol extract (25mg/ml)	50.79 ± 0.25	104.5 ± 0.28
VIII	Ethanol extract (50mg/ml)	33.77 ± 0.19***	71.36 ± 0.31

Statistical Analysis

Results are expressed as mean ± SEM were evaluated by one way ANOVA followed by Newman Kew's multiple range tests. Values of P < 0.001 were considered statistically significant.

Effect of CEDV and EEDV on Time for Paralysis (min).

Effect of CEDV and EEDV on Time taken for death (min).

Different stages in anthelmintic activity.**Stage3.****RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

The times for paralysis and when death of the worms occurred are provided in Table 2. Both chloroform and methanol extracts of *D. viscosa* aerial parts exhibited dose dependent and significant anthelmintic activity as compared with standard drug, albendazole. Chloroform extract required least time to causes paralysis and death of the earth worm followed when compared to the extracts from ethanol suggesting either higher concentrations of the compounds producing anthelmintic activity or more compounds with the activity.

The results of this work is limited to inability to report the actual compounds responsible for the activity reported because they were not isolated or investigated. However, certain intermediate polar constituents may be responsible for anthelmintic activity than polar constituents.

CONCLUSION

The chloroform and methanol extracts of *D. viscosa* have anthelmintic activity. This justifies the use of the plant in folklore remedies as an anthelmintic drug of natural origin. Further studies are required to isolate the possible phytoconstituents which may be responsible for the anthelmintic activity and to explore the possible mechanism of action.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to thank the Chairman of S. A. Raja pharmacy college, Rajas medical institutions, vadakkangulam, Tirunelveli District, Tamilnadu, India for necessary equipment for research, constant encouragement, facilities and support.

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